

EMBEDDED SENSORS FOR SMART MANUFACTURING AND SMART STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The use of embedded Fabry-Perot sensors for measuring strains and temperatures inside composites is explored. The principle of operation of such sensors is described, and the models required to relate the sensor output to the composite's temperature and strain are summarized. It is shown that with a single sensor and a single, constant wavelength light source, either the strain component along the sensor or the temperature change can be measured, but only under restricted conditions. The number and types of sensors needed to measure multiple strain components and temperature under a wide range of conditions are discussed. Data are also presented which demonstrate the validity of the models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Embedded fiber optic sensors have been studied extensively in recent years with a view of employing them to measure strain and temperature inside composites. The interest in such sensors is warranted because, in principle, they can provide information on local strains and temperature without significantly disturbing the material. There are, however, practical difficulties in using fiber optic sensors. The main problem is that a single sensor does not provide sufficient information for uniquely deducing the seven unknown parameters, namely the six strain components and the temperature. This review describes the difficulties, and suggests possible avenues for overcoming the problems. The present summary highlights only the essential features of embedded fiber optic temperature and strain sensors. For details the reader is referred to references 1 and 2. These references also contain a survey of the relevant literature.

2. INTRINSIC AND EXTRINSIC FABRY-PEROT SENSORS

Embedded fiber optic sensors generally operate on interferometric principles. The most common of these types of sensors are intrinsic and extrinsic Fabry-Perot sensors, which consist of a circular optical fiber embedded in the composite. There are two parallel, partially reflecting mirrors spliced into the optical fiber (Figure 1). The substance between the two mirrors is either glass (intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor) or air (extrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor).

A coherent laser beam of light is passed along the optical fiber. The intensity of light reflected from the first and second mirrors is measured. The objective is to deduce the strains and the temperature inside the composite from the measured changes in light intensity. To accomplish this, the light intensity must be related to the strains and temperature by appropriate expressions. These expressions are established via a model consisting of three submodels (Figure 2).

The first submodel relates the temperature change ΔT^∞ and the six strain components in the material $e_1^{m,\infty} \dots e_6^{m,\infty}$ surrounding the sensor to the temperature change and the strain components inside the fiber optic sensor.

The second submodel relates the changes in the temperature and strains inside the sensor to the changes in the length between the mirrors and in the refractive indices. This submodel includes two refractive indices, made necessary by shear strain effects.

The third submodel relates the relevant optical properties inside the sensor to the intensity of the reflected light I^R .

As noted above, details of the submodels are not given here but can be found in references 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Schematic of the embedded Fabry-Perot temperature and strain sensor.

Figure 2. Illustration of the three submodels.

2.1 Reflected Light Intensity

By using the three submodels, changes in the reflected light intensity can be calculated for specified changes in temperature and strain inside the composite. A user friendly computer code, SENSOR I, was written which can be used to perform the calculations. The code was verified by tests, in which an intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor was embedded in a Fiberite T300/976 graphite epoxy (0₄/45₂/ - 45₄)₅ plate. Strain gauges were also affixed to the surfaces of the plate.

Three types of tests were performed. First, a constant load was applied along the longer edge of the plate. Second, a constant load was applied along the shorter edge of the plate. Third, a varying load was applied along the longer edge of the plate. The changes in the light intensity were recorded. In addition, the strains were measured with surface mounted strain gauges. From these strains, the light intensities were also calculated by the SENSOR I code. Here, only the results obtained in the third type of test are shown (Figure 3). As can be seen, there is excellent agreement between the measured light intensity and the light intensity calculated by the model. The other two types of tests yielded similarly good agreements.

Figure 3. The measured and calculated intensities of the reflected light. Fabry-Perot sensor embedded in a T300/976 graphite-epoxy plate ($\Delta T = 0$).

2.2 Measurements of Temperature and Strain

With a single sensor and a single, constant wavelength light source, strain or temperature can be measured only under special circumstances. Axial strain can be measured when there is only one predominant stress in the material and it is in the direction of the embedded fiber optic sensor, while the temperature change is zero. Temperature change can be measured when only the applied temperature changes, while there are no stress changes inside the material. In the first case the stress, and in the second case the temperature change must vary (increase or decrease) with time continuously in a regular manner.

A computer code, SENSOR ST, was written which, under the above restricted conditions, provides either the strain or the temperature from the measured changes in light intensity. The code was verified by these tests. The first and second tests pertained to strain, the third to temperature.

In the first experiment load was applied uniformly along the graphite epoxy plate described above. In the second experiment, the sensor was embedded in a 16 plies thick unidirectional APC2/PEEK plate. Strain gauges were also mounted on the surfaces above and below the sensor. A line load was applied in a three-point bend test fixture.

In both tests, the outputs of strain gauges and the intensities of the reflected light were measured during loading. The axial strain at the location of the sensor was deduced from the strain gauge data. The strains were also calculated by the SENSOR ST code using the Fabry-Perot sensor data. The strains from the strain gauge data and from the intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor are compared in Figure 4. The strains given by the intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensors agree very well with the strains provided by the strain gauges. These results illustrate that embedded intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensors can be used to measure axial strain, at least under the limited condition when only an axial stress is applied.

Figure 4. Comparisons of the axial strains obtained from the intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor and the strain gauges ($\Delta T = 0$).

Figure 5. Comparison of the temperature changes obtained from the intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor and the thermocouple ($\sigma_1^{m,\infty} = \sigma_2^{m,\infty} \dots \sigma_6^{m,\infty} = 0$).

In the third experiment, temperature changes in the APC2/PEEK plate described above were measured by the embedded intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor and by a thermocouple embedded in the material next to the sensor. The plate was placed inside an oven and the temperature was increased. During heating, the outputs of the sensor and the thermocouple were recorded. The temperature changes given by the intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor (together with the SENSOR ST code) and by the thermocouple are compared in Figure 5. The temperature changes given by the intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensor agree very well with the temperature changes measured by the thermocouple.

3. CONCLUDING REMARKS

As the aforementioned summary indicates, intrinsic Fabry-Perot sensors consisting of a single fiber and a single, constant wavelength light source can only be used to measure either the axial strain component or the temperature change, but only under limited conditions. More than one fiber and more than one wavelength would be needed to measure strains and temperature changes accurately under complex thermal and mechanical loads. The SENSOR I and SENSOR ST codes provide tools for establishing the sensor and the light source characteristics required for such measurements. For example the number and types of sensors needed to determine two inplane strain components and the temperature were determined by the codes. The results showed that, depending on the sensor type, two to three sensors and two wavelengths are required to generate the data needed to determine simultaneously two inplane strain components and the temperature.

REFERENCES

1. K-S. Kim, L. P. Kollár and G.S. Springer, "A Model of Embedded Fiber Optic Fabry-Perot Temperature and Strain Sensors", *J. of Composite Materials*.
2. K-S. Kim, Y. Ismail and G.S. Springer, "Measurements of Strain and Temperature with Embedded Intrinsic Fabry-Perot Fiber-Optic Sensors", *J. of Composite Materials*.